

SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL BASIS OF THE FIGHT AGAINST RELIGIOUS EXTREMISM AND TERRORISM

Anvarjon Abduqaharov

Student of NavDPI "History" faculty

Annotation: In this article, in today's globalization and at a time when the transformation of international and regional conflicts continues, the issues of effective fight against terrorism and extremism are scientifically covered.

Key words: Extremism, terrorism, Shanghai, Anti-terrorist, jihadist, Criminal Code.

By the 21st century, extremism and terrorism have become one of the most dangerous social evils. The recent rise in extremism and terrorism shows how urgent this problem is. President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev also spoke about this issue: At the moment, the turbulent situation in some regions of the world is leading to the increase of population migration, which, in turn, is leading to the spread of terrorism and extremism and their becoming one of the global problems. In such a situation, maintaining our national statehood, independence, peaceful and peaceful life and security of our population is becoming the highest priority for us²³.

Chapter 2, Article 4 of our Constitution stipulates the issue of ensuring religious tolerance and peace in our country. The word "extremist" means "unbelievable", "excessive". The main characteristic of extremism is the promotion of views that are contrary to the values and norms accepted in society, extreme views and tendencies to measures.

Extremism undermines the country's development and civil harmony by rejecting tolerance, diversity and common -mindedness. Fanatics not only harm the political, economic or cultural spheres of social life, but also exert psychological pressure on the society in a massive way and spread the ideology of violence and aggression in the most terrible forms. From this point of view, one of the vital issues facing the state and society is to prevent religious conflicts in the society, to prevent any movement aimed at derailing the social stability in the country through the politicization and falsification of religion. From the first days of independence, the state of Uzbekistan has clearly and firmly defined its attitude to religion. Our General

²³ <https://xadicha.uz/uz/news/350>.

Council found its legal expression in the Constitution and the Law on Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations. In recent years, crimes against humanity have been committed in a number of countries of the world by various illegal armed organizations under the slogan of building an Islamic state. In particular, jihadist groups are widely using the Internet and social networks to attract new people to their ranks. Various Internet sites, forums and groups with different names organized on social sites such as Odnoklasnik, Twitter, and the You Tube portal are widely used. We are witnessing that they conduct interviews with people who spend their time on the Internet, who are temporarily unemployed, who are trying to earn money abroad, and who are dissatisfied with the social situation. It is known that Uzbekistan actively participates in the implementation of agreements aimed at combating extremism and terrorism adopted within the framework of a number of regional organizations. Political and legal documents related to the fight against terrorism and its elimination were signed within the framework of the UN, the Commonwealth of Independent States, and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. , systematically increasing the level and effectiveness of preventive and explanatory work in preventing the spread of the ideology of religious extremism and terrorism in our society has become a vital issue today²⁴.

It is worth noting that the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan or the Code of Administrative Responsibility and other laws clearly defined in our laws are punishable for committing and breaking the law. If a person who has fallen into a deluded current realizes his mistake in time, repents and helps solve the crime, he will be released from responsibility according to the relevant article of the Criminal Code. legal clarification work is being carried out aimed at preventing it from happening. This will be an important task of all our compatriots who are responsible for the future of our country²⁵.

Today, 2, 238 religious organizations belonging to 16 religious denominations are operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Of these, 2064 are Islamic, 157 are Christian, 8 are Jewish, 6 are Baha'i communities, one each is a Krishna Consciousness Society and a Buddhist temple. In addition to these, the interdenominational Bible society also operates. Religious organizations have the same right to operate, regardless of which denomination they belong to. The safe and

²⁴ . Fight against religious extremism, missionary work and international terrorism 1 M. Lafasov [, , a co.] ; Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T. : Publisher of the National Library of

²⁵ <https://qoraqalpoq.adliya.uz/uz/news/detail.php?ID=46298>

free operation of these religious organizations is a practical expression of the prevailing religious tolerance in our country²⁶.

Nowadays, there are many extremist and terrorist organizations in the world, unfortunately, some of them operate under the guise of Islam. Al-Qaeda, Hizbut-Tahrir al-Islami (Islamic Party of Freedom), al-Jihad, al-Takfir wal- Hijra (Takfir and emigration), Turkistan Islamic Movement are among them. , "Islami Jihad Ittihadi (Union of Islamic Jihad), Katibat al-Imam al-Bukhari (Battalion of Imam Bukhari), "Jamaat Ansarullah" (Association of the Helpers of Allah), "Jabhatun-Nusra" (Victory Front) and "Islamic State" such organizations can be counted²⁷. The decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated July 1, 2021 "On approval of the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan to fight against extremism and terrorism in 2021-2026" was adopted. "The purpose of the strategy is to ensure the implementation of an effective and simultaneously coordinated state policy to protect the constitutional system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, national security, fight against extremism and terrorism, and this is to ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens, " the document says. <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2021/07/06/strategy/> At present, initiatives to implement soft programs for repelling religious extremist movements are being implemented in many countries, in particular, in Ireland, Colombia, Norway, Germany, France, Sweden and other similar countries. The effectiveness of soft methods of repelling religious extremist movements can be seen in the strategy of the fight against extremism Contest in countries such as Sinai, Turkey, Malaysia, Indonesia, Great Britain, in the activities of the centers for the fight against extremism and terrorism such as Hidayat, Sawab in the United Arab Emirates, Munasakha in Saudi Arabia, and in the Arab Republic of Egypt. and it has been proven in practice within the activities of Al-Azhar Observatory and other centers for the fight against extremism²⁸.

In conclusion, in order to combat the problem of religious extremism and terrorism, which has become a danger for the whole world today, all the various measures to prevent extremism and terrorism should be systematic. Against the radical ideology, a religious idea that is understandable to everyone should be preserved. The religious views of some modern Muslims are politicized and

²⁶ <https://religions.uz/uz/news/detail?id=443>

²⁷ Combating terrorism and extremism tactics and methodology (Crime prevention activity for specialty): / J. S. Mukhtorov, B. F. Alimov, S. B. Khojakulov. Responsible editor Sh. T. Ikramov. T. : Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016. - 91 p.

²⁸ <https://iia.uz/oz/news/2174>

ideological. In this regard, it is very urgent to change their views from politics and ideology to socialization.

Used literature:

- 1) <https://xadicha.uz/uz/news/350>.
- 2) Fight against religious extremism, missionary work and international terrorism 1 M. Lafasov [, , ·a co.] ; Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T. : Publisher of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after A. Navoi. 2010.
- 3) <https://qoraqalpoq.adliya.uz/uz/news/detail.php?ID=46298>
- 4) Combating terrorism and extremism tactics and methodology (Crime prevention activity for specialty): / J. S. Mukhtorov, B. F. Alimov, S. B. Khojakulov. Responsible editor Sh. T. Ikramov. T. : Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016. - 91 p.
- 5) <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2021/07/06/strategy/>
- 6) <https://ii.au.uz/oz/news/2174>
- 7) Hoshimov Sh. J. , Samadov A. R. "Against religious extremism and terrorism "Spiritual-educational foundations of struggle" according to the training course: educational - methodological complex Samarkand 2010, p.

